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Career Management and Productivity of Public Health Institution: Evidence from Federal Medical Center Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between career management and productivity in Federal Medical Center Asaba, Delta State. Career management variables such as career planning, career development, career mentoring, career counseling and succession planning were employed as the independent variables while productivity was employed as the dependent variables. Related conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on theory of work adjustment. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study comprised 1778 employees of Federal Medical Center Asaba. Sample size of 327 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The data generated were analyzed using multiple regression technique. The study found that career planning, career development, career mentoring and succession planning had significant positive relationship with productivity while career counseling had an insignificant negative relationship with productivity. The study concludes that career management had significant positive relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center Asaba. The study recommends amongst others that the management of public health institutions should consider organizing for trainings and seminars for the employees this will help to increase employee skills and competence making them more willing to work harder for the success of the institution.

Keyword: Career Development, Career Planning, Career Mentoring, Career Counseling, Succession Planning.

Introduction

In today's competitive business environment, successful organizations regardless of size need employees who have the necessary knowledge and skills to make an effective contribution that drives the organization towards achieving a competitive edge (Kakui & Gachunga, 2016). In this dynamic business environment where people have become one of the critically important elements to gain competitive advantage, organizations are faced with new challenges in managing its human resources. Instead of focusing only on financial capabilities and product quality, Dreher and Dougherty (2001) suggested that organizations should engage in competitive search for the most capable employees. These capabilities can only be achieved through the development and implementation of effective human resource practices and strategies. In line with this Armstrong (2001) points out that today's dynamic environment requires continuous professional and managerial development. One of such human resources practices is career management. Khulida and Siti (2004)

noted that career management, one of the important elements in human resource management, has a great impact on organization.

Career management refers to the programs or activities provided by organizations to support their employees' career success (Kong, Cheung & Zhang, 2010). Dessler (2013) viewed career management as the process for enabling employees to better understand and develop their career skills and interests, and to use these skills and interests more effectively. Armstrong (2006) in his submission argued that career management is concerned with providing opportunities for people to progress and develop their careers and ensuring that the organization has the flow of talent it needs. Arguably, employees are the most valuable resource in contemporary organisations, and providing them with a long term stable career is a win-win situation for both organisations and their employees (Harlod & Amit, 2011). Hence, career management requires collaboration from both organisations as well as individuals in order to provide maximum benefit for both. The goals of most organizations are to provide their employees opportunities to develop their careers. Hiring the right human resources and having them develop simultaneously with the company's own growth have great impact on organizational outcomes especially productivity (Dialoke, Chiavoghi, & Ukonu, 2016). This creates continuity of management and knowledge and also an environment for employees to thrive and grow. It has been frequently shown that appreciation and growth can be stronger motivators for an employee than money and can result in reduced turnover rate, improved customer service and ultimately generates higher productivity for the company (Harlod & Amit, 2011).

Greenhaus, Callanan and Godshalk (2010) noted that the key aim of career management in the organization is to guide employee's career and how he/she can achieve enterprise effectiveness. In line with this, Osibanjo, Oyewunmi and Ojo (2014) contended that organization's must provide enabling environment for employees growth opportunities, which tend to motivate, promote, recognize, reward, and retain valuable employees. Employees should be given the opportunity for career advancement through career management in the organization to enable them plan for their future and that of the enterprise to avoid turnover which will affect production or service delivery.

Also, most organizations especially within the health sector have placed the responsibility of career development and advancement on the employees. They don't adopt a participatory approach to the management of employees and their careers to make sure they can respond to the different career demands in a competent and flexible way to increase the level of efficiency and effectiveness in the way the organization does its business. This has resulted in high number of employees without requisite skills to keep abreast of latest development in the health sector. Hence, Baruch (2006) has suggested that organizations should adjust their existing career management systems to be more in line with the contemporary views on organisations and careers, and not completely place all the responsibility on one of the parties. These changes will affect the level of commitment among employees towards an organization hence their productivity and choice to continue working with the organization.

Furthermore, the productivity of public health institutions has become a major source of concern to government and stakeholders in the health sector. The prevailing situation at the public health institution has been one of low work performance and poor service delivery. Prominent among the problems been witnessed in this sector is the issue of brain drain of the key professionals in the system. Most of the doctors and specialists in the system moved abroad in search of greener pasture. This has affected the availability of needed professionals in the system. Also governments have invested so much to reduce the high incidence of employees' turnover and improve career management practices. However, these practices have not fully addressed the issues of career management as the turnover of employees has remained high especially the migration of competent doctors and nurses to abroad in search of greener pasture.

Objectives

The objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between career management and productivity in Federal Medical Center Asaba. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between career management

variables (career planning, career development, career mentoring, career counseling and succession planning) and productivity in Federal Medical Center Asaba, Delta State.

Review of Related Literature

Career Management: Career management is defined as the process by which individuals collect information about values, interests, and skill strengths and weaknesses, identify a career goal, and engage in career strategies that increase the probability that career goals will be achieved (Greenhaus, Callanan & Godshalk, 2010). Eby, Allen and Brinley (2005) defined career management as “the process by which individuals develop insight into themselves and their environment, formulate career goals and strategies, and acquire feedback regarding career progress”. Similarly, Grobler et al. (2006) defined career management as “the process of designing and implementing goals, plans and strategies that enable HR professionals and managers to satisfy workforce needs and allow individuals to achieve their career objectives”.

Career management is concerned with the provision of opportunities for people to develop their abilities and their careers in order to ensure that the organization has the flow of talent it needs and to satisfy their own aspirations (Chew & Girardi, 2008). It is concerned with how careers progress the ways in which people move through their careers either upwards when they are promoted, or by enlarging or enriching their roles to take on greater responsibilities or make more use of their skills and abilities. It is based on an understanding of career dynamics and the integration of the needs of the organization with the needs of the individual employees.

Byars and Rue (2000) suggested that successful career management should include actions from three sources: the employee, the organization, and the employee’s immediate manager. Accordingly, employees’ responsibility is to prepare their own career plans, as career planning is not something one person can do for another. This is important because it is the employees who are going to put the plan into practice. Another source of successful career management suggested by Byars and Rue (2000) is the role of the organization. The organization’s responsibilities are to ensure a smooth delivery of necessary career related information and advice concerning possible career paths to carry out their career plans. In other words, an organization’s role is to create the environment that facilitates the development of individual career plans. The immediate manager’s responsibility, on the other hand, is to show an employee how to go about the process and help the employee evaluate the action taken (Byars & Rue, 2000).

Career Planning: Career planning is a continuous process of evaluating your current lifestyle, likes/dislikes, passions, skills, personality, dream job, and current job and career path and making corrections and improvements to better prepare for future steps in your career, as needed, or to make a career change (Harlod & Amit, 2011). Felix (2012) defined career planning the intentional process where an organization or individual gets to know of personal competencies and focuses on plans to achieve specific career goals. In another way, Career planning is a constant procedure of self-appraisal and objective setting planned by representative and business keeping in mind the end goal to work in accordance with hierarchical target. Career planning includes both representative and business interfacing together to recognize objectives, furthermore create techniques required to satisfy distinguished objective (Leibowitz cited in Khadijetou, 2016). Career planning involves the definition of career paths – the routes people can take to advance their careers within an organization. It uses all the information provided by the organization’s assessments of requirements, the assessments of performance and potential and management succession plans, and translates it into the form of individual career development programmes and general arrangements for management development, career counseling and mentoring (Baruch 2006).

Career Development: Career development is defined as “an ongoing, formalized effort by an organization that focuses on developing and enriching the organization’s human resources in light of both the employees’ and the organization’s needs” (Byars & Rue, 2000).

Career development is perceived like joint effort between the individual employee and the organization (Lyria, Namusonge & Karanja, 2017). Career development describes the lifelong process of managing life, learning and work. Fieldman and Thomas (2004) define career development as a progression of exercises or the continuous procedure of building up one's vocation. The procedure involves preparing new aptitudes, moving to higher occupation obligations; roll out a profession improvement with a similar association, or beginning one's business. Career development is an effective way to foster future leaders within organization with relevant skills and experience that will be required to implement organization strategies (Khadijetou, 2016). The programs of career development are the processes through which employees' career goals and aspirations are nurtured to fulfillment; and at the same time aligning these career goals with the organizational needs, opportunities and goals (Schultze & Miller, 2006).

Career Mentoring: Career mentoring is another career management practice adopted by many organizations. Aneeq (2012) defined career mentoring as the process of developing formal relationships between junior and senior members of an organization. Yang & Long (2006) defines mentoring as a professional activity, a trusted relationship, and a meaningful commitment. Mentoring practice as we know it today is loosely modeled on the historical craft man apprentice relationship, where young people learned. Mentoring relationship have a great potential to enhance the development of young individuals in both early and middle career stage (Yang & Long 2006).

Career Mentoring usually takes the form of a senior or experienced employee taking a supporting role in the development of a new or inexperienced employee. It can be formal or informal and relies on the development of a positive advisory relationship. As such it includes the skills of coaching, facilitating, counseling and networking. Mentoring is part of a range of career development activities which organizations engage in to identify, develop, engage, retain and deploy the more talented individuals (Warren, 2006). The career mentoring relationship is most often oriented towards an exchange of wisdom, support, learning or guidance for the purpose of career growth and increase employee performance and sometimes it is used to achieve strategic goals (Parsloe & Wry, 2000). It is usually a process where the worker is exposed to an individual who is like a role model. The worker under mentoring is expected to learn how to be a better person at the work place and in private life. Career mentoring is based on counseling and supports learners and helps them to develop their own approach and solutions to problems (Hall, 2005).

Career Counseling: Career counseling according to Khadijektou (2016) is "career education awareness is delivered in edification organizations, workplaces, and occasionally, in the community by organizations career counselors". The OECD Career Guidance Policy Review (2003) defines career counseling as services and practice intended to assist individuals, of any age and at any point throughout their lives, to make educational, training and occupational choices and to manage their careers" (Aisenson et al 2004). This definition includes making information about the labour market and about educational and employment opportunities more accessible by organizing it, systematizing it and having it available when and where people need it. It also includes assisting people to reflect on their aspirations, interests, competencies, personal attributes, qualifications and abilities and to match these with available training and employment opportunities. Career counseling brings the two together and stresses the interaction between learning and work. Hansen further suggests that career guidance activities in high-income countries are categorized into five specialties: Career information which deals with all the information necessary to plan for, obtain and keep employment, whether paid or voluntary. Career counseling is a systematic approach to facilitating the career decision making and job search process. It is a partnership between you and your career counselor designed to assist you in making important decisions about career.

Succession Planning: Succession planning was first introduced by Fayol who believed if succession planning needs were ignored, organizations would not be prepared to make necessary transitions (Rothwell, 2010). It is an organized process comprising the identification and preparation of potential successor to assume new role

(Garman & Glawe, 2004). In defining succession planning, Hackett (1997) asserts that it is concerned with identifying the key jobs in one organization and ensuring that if anything, planned or unplanned were to remove the present job holder from his post, there would be someone ready to take the lost position.

Belcourt and McBey (2007) see succession planning as the process of identifying employees who have the potential to assume key positions in the organization and preparing them for these positions. The identification of talent is always paired with on-going programs to develop that talent. Likewise, succession planning defined as “deliberate and systematic effort by an organization to ensure leadership continuity in key positions, retain and develop intellectual and knowledge capital for the future and encourage individual” (Rothwell, 2010). It is argued that succession planning is no longer limited to top managers, nowadays need to successor for every job in the organization is evident, especially with more involvement of employees to the organization and distribution of decision making to empowered employees across organizations.

Productivity: Productivity measures how efficiently resources are employed, It is defined as the ratio of a specific measure of output to a specific measure of input per unit of labour and is measured as total output divided by the members of units of labour employed to produce that output Productivity is the relationship between the output generated by a production or service system and the input provided to create this output. This productivity is defined as the efficient use of resources labor, capital, land, material, materials, energy, and information—in the production of various goods and service (Prokopenko, 2007). Williams (2000) says that productivity is the relationship between output of goods and services and input of resources, human and non-human, used in the production process. In other words, productivity is the ratio of output to input. The higher the numerical value of this ratio, the greater the productivity. Thus, productivity can be applied at any level, whether for individuals, for work unit, for the organization.

The Productivity is the driving force behind an organization’s growth and profitability. Productivity is the relationship between output of goods and services of workers of the organization and input of resources, human and non-human, used in the production process. In other words, productivity is the ratio of output to input. The higher the numerical value of this ratio, the greater the productivity (Williams, 2000).The importance of higher productivity of the employees in public enterprise cannot be overemphasized, which include the following; Higher incomes and profit; Higher earnings; Increased supplies of both consumer and capital goods at lower costs and lower prices; Ultimate shorter hours of work and improvements in working and living conditions; Strengthening the general economic foundation of workers (Nwachukwu, 2009). The existence of any organization is anchored on productivity and its importance cannot be overemphasized. It is the wish of every organization to be productive because productivity forms the cardinal essence for which every organization exist. To attain or increase productivity, it has led many organizations into constant reshuffling practice.

Theoretical Framework

This study derived its theoretical foundation from the theory of work adjustment. This theory was developed in the 1950s by University of Minnesota work adjustment project (Dawis, 2005). Brown (2003) argues that the theory was one of the most advanced for career development with it being suitable for valuation tools. The Theory of Work Adjustment gives a model for hypothesizing the networking of people and work environment and it is regarded as a person-environment network model which is a reciprocal relationship (Swanson & Schneider, 2013). Betz (2008) observes that the focus of Theory of Work Adjustment is career planning on individual competencies and the environmental skill requirements. Further, the theory is about the person planning for work environments that would meet his/her needs and in response the environment plans for people who can meet the demands of the organization. Therefore, career development is hypothesized as a continuous process of work adjustment brought about by dissatisfaction of both parties (Dawis, 2005).

The theory argues that career development can be achieved when an individual searches for organizations (environment) that align with perceived requirement; while the organizations (environment) also seek for individuals that possess expected requirement of the organization. However, mutual agreement should

be established among the parties involved. In modern times, Theory of Work Adjustment has been linked to positive psychology because of its concern for satisfaction (Swanson & Scheneider, 2013). Satisfaction promotes employee well-being and prevents work stress. Dawis (2005) contends that aside from career planning, the theory of work adjustment is also concerned with actual job performance. The researcher argued that the matching of personal needs to the work environment increases job satisfaction for an employee leading to improved work performance. Henceforth, there has to be a coherent adjustment of employee needs to their work environment for them to perform effectively at their roles. This involves appropriate career planning to enable a great fit between them and their work environment. Felix (2012) argues that career planning assists the organizations in the placing of employees in jobs that match their individual career preferences, needs and goals which is the main idea of the theory of work adjustment (Dawis, 2005).

Empirical Review

The relationship between career management and productivity has attracted much scholarly attention. Dialoke, Chiavoghi, and Ukonu (2016) investigated the effects of employee career management on organisational performance using selected banks in Umuahia, Abia State. In this study, career development and career counseling were employed as the explanatory variables while organizational performance was employed as the dependent variable. 213 bank workers were sampled for the study. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was employed for data analysis using SPSS. The study found that employee career management is significantly associated with organisational performance. The study concluded that employee career management promotes organisational performance of banks.

Kakui and Gachunga (2016) examined the effects of career development on employee performance in National Cereals and Produce Board, Kenya. Descriptive survey design was adopted. A total of 200 employees of National Cereals and Produce Board head office in Nairobi were sampled for the study. Descriptive statistics was employed in analyzing the data. The study revealed that on job training influences the performance of an employee by expansion of key competencies, job specification, leads to motivation, reduces intimidation, provides additional skills knowledge and capabilities and employees are able to network. The study revealed that career mentoring affects employee performance.

Oduma and Were (2014) examined the influence of career development on employee performance in the public university in Kenyatta University. In this study, training, career mentoring, job orientation and career advancement were employed as the explanatory variables while employee performance was employed as the dependent variable. A total of 4874 teaching and non-teaching staff Kenyatta University were sampled for the study. The study adopted descriptive research design. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data. The study established that training, career mentoring, job orientation and career advancement had a positive impact on employee performance in the public university in Kenya.

Lyria, Namusonge and Karanja (2017) examined the effect of career management on organizational performance of firms listed in the Nairobi Securities Exchange. In this study, succession planning and job rotation were employed as the independent variable while profit and growth (proxy for organizational performance) was employed as the dependent variable. The study adopted descriptive and correlation survey research designs. A total of 224 top managers of listed companies in the NSE were sampled for the study. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data. The study found a strong and positive relationship between career management and organization performance of all listed companies. Organizational performance was positively correlated with career management.

Rønn (2010) examined the moderating effect of openness to experience on the relationship between career management and organisational commitment. Correlation and multiple regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data. Results showed that openness to experience did not moderate the relationship between organisational career management and commitment. However, openness to experience did moderate the effect of commitment on individual's career self-management activities (both internally and externally oriented activities).

Harlod and Amit (2011) examined career management, employee development and performance in Indian information technology organizations. The study aimed to investigate relationship between career planning, performance and employee growth and explores the alignment between individual and organization’s career planning. 100 employees from five Indian IT companies were sampled for the study. Descriptive statistics and principal component analysis was employed in analyzing the data. It was found that Career guidance, leadership roles, network building, developing new skills, taking up special assignments and receiving productive feedback from the boss play the most important role in making the careen path easier and also aids in the performance and employee growth. Will to seek information, introspecting past experience, experimenting new work roles, and discussing career interest with superiors and colleagues play a moderate role in career planning and performance of the employees.

Methods

This study adopted survey research design. This study was carried out in Delta State at Federal Medical Center Asaba. Asaba is the administrative capital of Delta State. The population of study is made up of 1778 employees of Federal Medical Center Asaba (Human Resources Department, FMC, 2022). Taro Yamane’s formula was employed to get a sample size of 327. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. The data generated were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The accompanying regression model is stated below

$$PD = a + \beta_1CP + \beta_2CD + \beta_3CM + \beta_4CC + \beta_5SP + e$$

Where;

PD = Productivity

CP = Career Planning

CD = Career Development

CM = Career Mentoring

CC = Career Counseling

SP = Succession Planning

a = constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = beta coefficients

e = error term

Results

The regression results are presented in the tables below.

Table 1: Summary of Regression Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.840 ^a	.706	.703	1.867	1.904

Source: SPSS Version 21

a. Predictors: (Constant), Career Planning, Career Development, Career Mentoring, Career Counseling, Succession Planning

b. Dependent Variable: Productivity

The table above shows that summary of the regression result. The R square (R^2) value of 0.706 indicates that 70.6 percent of the variations in productivity are explained by variations in career planning, career development, career mentoring, career counseling and succession planning. Similarly, R square adjusted value of 0.703 indicates that 70.3% of variation in the dependent variable is accounted by variation in the independent variable, all things been equal. The Durbin-Watson statistics which is employed to check for autocorrelation recorded 1.904 as its value which is within the acceptable threshold. This shows that the variables used in the model are not auto-correlated and are therefore, reliable for predications.

Table 2: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4704.657	5	940.931	269.822	.000 ^a
	Residual	1959.822	322	3.487		
	Total	6664.479	327			

Source: SPSS Version 21

a. Predictors: (Constant), Career Planning, Career Development, Career Mentoring, Career Counseling, Succession Planning

b. Dependent Variable: Productivity

Table 2 above indicates that the F-test which test the overall significance of the model recorded a value of 269.822 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significant. This indicates that career planning, career development, career mentoring, career counseling and succession planning can collectively explain the variations in productivity. This indicates that career management has significant relationship with productivity of Federal Medical Center Asaba.

Table 3 Coefficients of the Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.024	1.149		11.335	.000
	Career Counseling	-.014	.038	-.011	-.361	.718
	Career Planning	.089	.038	.148	2.322	.021
	Career Development	.177	.042	.316	4.170	.000
	Career Mentoring	.317	.049	.673	6.450	.000
	Succession Planning	.573	.056	.391	10.218	.000

Source: SPSS Version 21

a. Dependent Variable: Productivity

Career planning recorded a t-statistics value of 2.322 with an alpha value of 0.021 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that career planning has significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. Career development has a t-statistics value of 4.170 with an alpha value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. This implies that career development has a significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba.

Career mentoring recorded a t-statistic value of 6.450 which a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. This implies that career mentoring has a significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. Career counseling recorded a t-statistics value of 0.361 with a probability value of 0.718 which is statistically insignificant. Hence, career counseling has no significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. Succession planning recorded a t-statistics value of 10.218 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. This implies that succession planning has a significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that career planning has significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. This agrees with the findings of Harlod and Amit (2011) that career planning has significant relationship with performance. This further agrees with the findings of Mwashila (2017) that career planning have a significant influence on academic staff performance in public universities. This implies that with effect

career planning in public health organization, the productivity of both the organization and the employees will improve significantly.

Similarly, career development was found to have significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. This tally with the findings of Dialoke, Chiavoghi, and Ukonu (2016) that career development is significantly associated with organisational performance. This also agrees with the findings of Mohd and Khulida (2017) that career development practice impact on employees' performance in Malaysian local authority. The findings of Suyanto, Ketut and Nengah (2018) that career development has positive and significant effect on employee performance is in line with that of the present study. This findings implies that when employees' career are effectively developed, both the employees and organizations productivity will improve.

The study further revealed that career mentoring has a significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. This collaborates the findings of Oduma and Were (2014) that career mentoring had a positive impact on employee performance in the public university in Kenya. This further corroborates the findings of Mark and Nzulwa (2018) that coaching/mentoring has significant positive effect on employee performance. This implies that career mentoring has significant positive relationship with the productivity of both the employees and the organization.

Career counseling was found to have an insignificant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. This agrees with the findings of Mark and Nzulwa (2018) that career counseling has negative and insignificant effect on employee performance in National Hospital Insurance Fund, Kenya. This finding disagrees with the findings of Dialoke, Chiavoghi, and Ukonu (2016) that career counseling is significantly associated with organisational performance. Consequently, public health institutions in Anambra State have to improve their career counseling services to their employees so that productivity can be improved.

Finally, succession planning was found to have significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. This is in line with the findings of Lyria, Namusonge and Karanja (2017) that succession planning has a strong and positive relationship with organization performance. This also agrees with the findings of Baba and Edwinah (2016) that careful and predetermined succession of leadership is imperative to the maintenance of performance standards. It is also in line with the position of Nwosu (2014) that through succession planning, the quantity and quality of leaders are identified, fully capable, and ready to contribute to the effective performance of a business in future.

Conclusion

This work examined career management and productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba, Delta State. Data generated from the employees of Federal Medical Center, Asaba were tested using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The study found that career planning has a significant relationship with productivity. Career development was found to have significant relationship with productivity. Similarly, career mentoring was also found to have significant relationship with productivity. The study also revealed that career counseling has no significant relationship with productivity. Also, succession planning has a significant relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba.

Banking on the aforementioned findings, the study concludes that career management has a significant positive relationship with productivity in Federal Medical Center, Asaba. Therefore, by designing an effective career management system, public health institutions have the opportunity to improve the skills and competences of their employees who requires sophisticated and technical knowledge to effectively carry out their tasks. Effective career management in public health institutions will help to reduce the incidence of brain drain as the employees have the opportunity to develop and improve on their competences thereby improving the productivity of public health organizations.

Based on the findings, the study recommends that the management of public health institutions should consider organizing for trainings and seminars for the employees this will help to increase employee skills and competence making them more willing to work harder for the success of the institution. Also, the management of public health institutions should remain focused on developing the career counseling services to its

employees; this will boost the morale and ultimately the productivity of staff. Instituting career planning programmes will enable a deeper focus on an employee's aims and aspirations—from identification of the handicaps being faced by an employee in accomplishing his goals to the solutions in terms of re-skilling or reassignment. Public health institutions should increase their support for career development activities to improve employees' performance. This can be done through increase in funding of employee career activities such as further studies, research, publications and conferences expenses. Finally, public health institutions should plan effectively for its succession by grooming seasoned employees for the task ahead in order not to bring disruption in the organizational activities.

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